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Assessment of the Changes in the Quantity and Flow Regimes of the Available Water Resources of the Kashkadarya River under the Conditions of Climate Change

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***Abstract:** The article examines the current and long-term changes in the quantity and flow regimes of water resources in the context of the projected climate changes in the Kashkadarya basin region. The levels and mineralization of groundwater in irrigated agricultural fields within the Kashkadarya River basin were determined. Based on data obtained from the hydroposts of the Kashkadarya River, annual analysis results were obtained, and the flow quantity of the river was determined accordingly. The possibilities of applying improved furrow and pressurized irrigation methods for growing agricultural crops were studied by examining the soil and climatic conditions of the Kashkadarya River basin, accurately assessing the amount of water used for irrigation during the season, investigating the efficiency of furrow and pressurized irrigation methods through field research, evaluating the potential for water-saving practices, and conducting field experiments to enhance the productivity of irrigated areas and the utilized water.*

The study predicts changes in the soil-reclamation conditions of irrigated agricultural fields under water-saving irrigation methods to mitigate increasing water scarcity. Recommendations will be developed to improve the productivity of irrigated fields and the water used in these fields. The analysis of groundwater mineralization levels in the irrigated agricultural fields of Kashkadarya River basin showed that in the irrigated fields of Qarshi district, 49% (24,630 ha) of the groundwater mineralization levels are in the range of 1 - 3 g/l, 40% are 3 - 5 g/l, and 11% are 5 - 10 g/l. In Kamashi district, 30% of the irrigated fields have groundwater mineralization levels of 0 - 1 g/l, 27%

have 1 - 3 g/l, 16% have 3 - 5 g/l, 25% have 5 - 10 g/l, and 2% have more than 10 g/l. In Kitob district, almost all (100%) irrigated fields have groundwater mineralization levels not exceeding 0 - 1 g/l. This indicates that Kitob district, being located in the area where groundwater is formed, has unchanged mineralization levels, while in Kamashi and Qarshi districts, located in the middle and lower reaches, the mineralization of groundwater is increasing.

Key words: natural-climatic conditions, meteorological indicators, water-saving technologies, drip irrigation system, soil temperature, moisture, field experimental plot, river basin, salinization, groundwater, irrigation water quantity, water balance, productivity, evaporation, water resources, agriculture, irrigation, climate change, irrigation water productivity, efficient water use, water-saving irrigation technologies.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is one of the main sectors of Uzbekistan's economy, situated in an arid region. Nearly 90% of the water resources utilized in the country are used for agriculture. Therefore, water resources are fundamental to the sustainable development of Uzbekistan's economy [1-3]. The total area of agricultural land in Uzbekistan is approximately 4.3 million hectares. With the rapid increase in the population and the projected climate changes, the decreasing water resources year by year make it extremely important to ensure sufficient food supply for the population [4-6]. Efficient use of water resources in agricultural irrigation has become one of the most pressing tasks for the country. Enhancing the productivity of the existing water used in agriculture is crucial and can be achieved by widely implementing water-saving irrigation methods in crop cultivation [7-8].

The studied area of the Kashkadarya River can currently be divided into natural and anthropogenic hydrographic branches. The Kashkadarya River and its tributaries, including Jinnidaryo, Oqsuv, Tanxozdaryo, Yakkabog'daryo, Guzordaryo, Langar, and others, are the main natural sources of water for the oasis [9-11].

On the example of the Karshi desert, many scientists have conducted research, and we have considered the results of modeling [12]. The area of irrigated land has steadily expanded from 1970 to 1995, and this trend continues today. The growth of gray lands in the Nishon, Mirishkor, Kasbi, and Mubarak districts has driven this expansion. The modeling process took into account indicators of groundwater level fluctuations across the region. Throughout the study period, it was found that increased infiltration in newly developed lands primarily contributed to the accumulation of groundwater reserves. The storage capacity of groundwater increased significantly, particularly in the initial 10 years, rising from 3,696 m³/day to 11,097 m³/day. In the subsequent 25 years, the accumulation varied, ranging from 9.99 m³/day to 7,235 m³/day, ultimately decreasing to 3,558 m³/day by the end of the modeling period [13-15].

Iqlimning o'zgarishi bo'yicha olib borilgan tadqiqotlarda Qashqadaryo viloyati uchun bazi bir xulosalar keltirilgan. Average Temperature Decrease: The average temperature decreased from 14.53 °C between 2006-2010 to 14.40 °C between 2011-2015. Monthly Average Maximum Temperature: There is an increase in the monthly average maximum temperature in January, March, September, November, and December from east to west. The minimum and maximum precipitation amounts were 11.23 mm and 55.91 mm, respectively, between 2006-2010. These amounts increased to 11.96 mm and 60.28 mm, respectively, during 2011-2015 [16].

The amount of water in the beginning, middle and end parts of the Kashkadarya river was studied in terms of water quality. The quality of the water in the upper part of the river is better than the quality of the water in the lower part. Midsections have become a source of pollution. River water pollution is mainly caused by the discharge of waste water into the river by consumers. They are mainly wastewater from industrial enterprises and the population. It is necessary to establish the disposal of wastewater in the treated state and to maintain the quality of the water through at least biological treatment methods [17-19].

Result and their experience

In the Qashqadaryo region, there are 3122 rivers and streams, with 149 rivers longer than 10 km, 33 of which are longer than 20 km. The main river of the region is considered to be the Qashqadaryo River, with a length of 332 km and a drainage area of 8750 km². The Qashqadaryo River originates in the western part of the Hisor Mountains at an elevation of 3000 meters, starting as a small stream and flowing through Muborak before finally emptying into sand dunes without reaching Muborak. Currently, due to excessive water consumption for irrigation, its summer flow is significantly lower than before. One of the major tributaries of the Qashqadaryo is the Yakkabog' River, which starts from the southwest part of the Hisor Mountains, with a length of 108 km and a basin area of 1060 km². In terms of river discharge, the Yakkabog' River ranks second in the Qashqadaryo basin after the Oqsuv River. Before reaching the Qashqadaryo River, the Yakkabog' River splits into two branches, the Qorabog' River flowing westward and the Qizilsuv River flowing northwestward, joining the Tanxoz River and eventually merging into the Qashqadaryo River.

1-Table The main morphometric characteristics of the hydrographic zones of the Qashqadaryo basin.

T.r.	Name of River	Estaury	Lq, km	L, km	F, km ²	length of rivers smaller than 10 km	
						number	Total length, km
1	Qashqadaryo	It mingles into the sand	-	378	12000	138	286
2	Jinnidaryo	Qashqadaryo (ch)	313	52	344	107	192
3	Qorabuloq	Qashqadaryo (ch)*	-	16	22	-	-
4	Oqdaryo	Qashqadaryo (ch)	286	104	1280	40	86
5	Qorasuv	Oqdaryo (ch)	39	33	139	51	56
6	Tanxozdaryo	Qashqadaryo (ch)	274	93	1910	136	273
7	Yakkabog'daryo	Tanxazdaryo (ch)	12	99	1180	121	283
8	To'rna	Yakkabog'daryo (ch)	24	35	186	67	106
9	Guldara	Qizildaryo (ch)*	-	40	276	16	56
10	Jar	Qashqadaryo (o')	266	64	348	103	112
11	Lyangar	Qashqadaryo (ch)*	-	39	243	33	36
12	Kichikuradaryo	G'uzordaryo (ch)	86	114	1670	134	223
13	Kattauradaryo	G'uzordaryo (o')	86	100	1370	149	307
14	Qumdaryo	Qashqadaryo (o')*	-	103	866	51	59

Izoh: * - bosh daryoga yetib bormaydi; Lq, km – quyilishidan bo'lgan masofa; L – daryo uzunligi; F – suv yig'ish maydoni.

The flow of the Yakkabog' River is generated by seasonal snow and glacier melts. In both cases, part of the water generated infiltrates into the ground, part is intercepted, and only the remaining part contributes to river flow. Significant river flow occurs when the timing of rainfall or the melting pattern of snow and glaciers coincides with infiltration and interception.

Based on the results of calculations regarding the annual distribution of the Yakkabog' River flow by months, diagrams illustrating the monthly distribution of river flow throughout the year were drawn. These diagrams depict how the river flow varies month by month over the course of the year (1-image).

1-image The annual distribution of the flow of the Yakkabog' River measured at the Tatar hydrological station by months

The main water artery of the studied region is referred to as the Qashqadaryo River. It originates from the Aba-Zorak and Podum valleys of the Zarafshan Range at an elevation of 2088 meters. The river spans a length of 332 km and covers a drainage area of 8750 km². Starting from the western part of the Hisor Mountains at an altitude of 3000 meters, the Qashqadaryo River begins modestly and flows into sand dunes before reaching Muborak. Currently, its summer flow is significantly diminished due to extensive water usage for irrigation purposes, leaving it relatively high upstream.

Large tributaries of Kashkadarya such as Jinnidarya, Aksuvdarya, Tankhozdarya, Yakkabogdarya, Guzordarya provide it with water. Kashkadarya, which started as a small stream, becomes the largest river of the basin as a result of the joining of tributaries. Below we will focus on the main tributaries of Kashkadarya:

Jinnidaryo is the first and relatively large left tributary of Qashqadaryo. The river is 57 km long and its watershed covers an area of 367 km². Jinnidaryo originates from the junction of several springs and streams between the peaks of Oqota (2919 m) and Shirdag' (2696 m), the highest points of the watershed. As it flows westward, the elevation of the river basin gradually decreases.

The Oqsuv River is 115 km long, with a watershed area of 1050 km² where it collects water. It is considered the most significant left tributary of the Qashqadaryo River, with an average annual water

flow of 12.3 m³/s. It is prone to seasonal fluctuations due to snowmelt and spring rains. Consequently, the river experiences its peak flow from May to June, while the lowest water levels occur during the months of December to February.

Tanhozdiyaryo originates from the southern-western part of Lake Qoziko‘l in the Hissar Mountains. It stretches for 104 km and drains an area of 452 km². Tanhozdiyaryo is affected by snowmelt and occasional spring rains. The river experiences its peak water flow from May to June, with the lowest levels typically occurring from January to February.

Yakkabog‘diyaryo also begins in the southern-western part of the Hissar Mountains, similar to Tanhozdiyaryo. It stretches for 108 km and covers a watershed area of 1060 km². In terms of river flow, Yakkabog‘diyaryo ranks second in significance within the Qashqadaryo basin, following Oqsuvdiyaryo. Yakkabog‘diyaryo flows into two rivers before reaching Qashqadaryo: Qorabog‘ and Qizilsuv. The Qorabog‘ River flows westward and eventually joins the Sug‘orish River. The Qizilsuv River flows northwest, merges with the Tanhozdiyaryo, and then continues to join the Qashqadaryo River downstream.

G‘uzordiyaryo originates from the continuation of the Hissar Range, specifically from the junction of the Kattao‘ra and Kichiko‘ra rivers. The river is 68 km long and drains a watershed area of 3170 km². It is fed by snowmelt. The river experiences high water levels primarily from March to May, while its lowest water levels occur around September to October.

2-image. Hydrological map of Kashkadarya region

The basin has a contemporary Amu Darya riverbed and a partially open structure towards the Zarafshan delta. Groundwaters are similarly arranged in a radial pattern. The main direction of their movement is towards the Shorsu pastures on the right bank, while on the left bank, they flow towards the Amu Darya riverbed and Lake Dengizkol. Their depth decreases from the mountain peaks to the modern Qashqadaryo riverbed (from 100 to 0.0 meters). The chemical composition of the waters correlates with decreasing salinity and is affected by easily soluble salts in transit zones. Water

mineralization ranges from 3 to over 10 grams per liter, primarily comprising sulfate and sodium types. Chuchuk waters (Potable) in the Qashqadaryo basin (Chuchuk lagoons) extend up to Qarshi city in the east, with restricted amounts in the west, being distributed in small lagoons alongside river lengths and major canals.

According to the conditions of formation and consumption based on temporary and late neogene deposits, the subsurface waters in the region are categorized into artesian waters and interlayer waters.

Sizot waters are limited by alluvial, alluvial-proluvial, proluvial deposits of the Quaternary period, in the southern part of the region - by sandstones and sandstone siltstones of the Upper Neogene period. Aqueous rocks include gravels, different-grained sands, sandy loams, loams. The depth of underground water in the region is from 1 m to 100 m and more, in the main part it is 10-80 m. The smallest depth of underground water formation was recorded in the Charagil lowland and the steep part of Kashkadarya, as well as in the irrigated areas of the proluvial plain. Groundwater saturation is carried out mainly from the gravel part of the cone-outlet of Guzardarya and large channels such as Kashkadarya and Fayzabad, Qamashi, Denov, Beshkent. The source of groundwater saturation in areas close to the surface of the earth is due to atmospheric precipitation and absorption of water used for irrigation in irrigated areas.

Subsurface waters, primarily allocated for irrigation within the contemporary watercourse of the Amu Darya, are present throughout much of the region. Additionally, subsurface waters in the vicinity of the Charagil lowlands are utilized for irrigation and transpiration purposes. The mineralization levels of groundwater vary significantly, ranging from 0.5 to 30 g/l, with concentrated areas in low-lying regions reaching up to 50.78 g/l. Dry residues range from 0.5-1.0 g/l to 1.0-3.0 g/l for brackish and slightly mineralized waters, which are distributed via major canals like Denov, Fayzli, and Fayzobod, covering areas up to 3 km wide. Sulfate, sulfate-chloride, and chloride are primarily found in subsurface waters according to their mineralization. Pressurized watercourses, such as the Neogene-era sands, alevrolites, and clay deposits at depths of 50-330 meters, are categorized as interlayered (artesian) waters. Paleogene-era silty deposits serve as local water sources. Mineralization levels of pressurized waters vary widely, with solid residue contents ranging from 1-3 g/l to 10-15 g/l, with mineral composition characteristics varying from sulfate-sodium to chloride-sodium.

The value of the water module is determined by the water cycle of evaporation and condensation. In winter and during prolonged droughts, many rivers freeze with underground water. The role of surface water in flooding is minimal in strong and long-lasting rainfalls. The maximum value of the water module corresponds to the rainwater period, while the minimum corresponds to the winter period.

In the upper part of Qashqadaryo, there are no polluting factors. The quality of river water deteriorates after the Chimqurgon water reservoir, following the addition of left bank and collector canals like Qorabog' soy, Qillisoy, Qorasuv, and Xudoyzot.

In the Kitob-Shakhrisabz plain of the Oqdaryo River, the main source of groundwater recharge comes from the natural outflows of groundwater. The water quality of the Oqdaryo River's surface water is very good because it is not affected by pollution in the formation zone of groundwater discharge.

Tanhozardaryo is considered the left tributary of the Qashqadaryo River. The water coming from Tanhozardaryo is discharged in a natural stable hydrochemical regime without pollution being observed.

In this study, primary attention is directed towards researching the hydrography of the Qashqadaryo basin, with a focus on understanding the annual variations in the flow of the Qashqadaryo River and its tributaries. For this purpose, data on water consumption for the Qashqadaryo River and its tributaries

were collected. Based on the compiled information, the long-term fluctuations in the flow of the Qashqadaryo River and its tributaries were analyzed.

1-graph. Graph of annual changes in Kashkadarya river flow (Varganza-Kashkadarya hydropost).

Data from hydro-posts in the Qashqadaryo River basin were analyzed over the years. Information from the Varganza hydro-post indicates significantly low annual flows. Average data for 2023 show a decrease compared to Yakkabog‘daryo by 2.644 m³/s annually, Tanhozdaryo-Katag‘daryo by 1.636 m³/s annually, and Oqsuvdaryo-Khazarnova hydro-posts by 6.23 m³/s annually.

2-graph. Graph of the annual change of Tankhozdarya river flow (Tankhozdarya-Katagon hydropost).

Analyzing the data of the Tankhozdarya-Katagon hydroposts by years, the following results were obtained: 5.78 m³/s in 2019, this indicator decreased to 2.13 m³/s in 2021, and 1.956 m³/s in 2023 (33.84% compared to 2019).

3-graph. Graph of annual changes in Aksuvdarya river flow (Aksuvdarya-Khazarnova hydropost).

In the changes in the data of the Oksuvdarya-Khazarnova hydropost, we can see the years of heavy rain in 2019-2020 with an average of 12.6 m³/s year. Until 2023, we will see a decreasing pattern for at least a few years. The result of 2023 shows 6.55 m³/s year

4-graph. Graph of annual fluctuations of Yakkaboghdarya river flow (Yakkaboghdaryo-Tatar hydropost).

According to the data of Yakkaboghdarya, the change of the river is significant, that is, in 2019, the average consumption was 9.44 m³/s year, and in 2020, it can be seen that it decreased to 4.43 m³/s year. This result has decreased by 1.85 m³/s year (63%) by 2021 compared to 2020. The difference for 2022-2023 shows 0.341 m³/s year, but this is not a good result because we can see a decrease of 6.476 m³/s year compared to 2019.

5-graph. Graph of annual fluctuations of Jinnidarya river flow (Jinnidarya-Jauz hydropost).

The annual flow change at the Jinni Darya-Jauz hydrostation showed almost a very small difference compared to the Varganza Darya hydrostation. 2019 was a year of 1.41 m³/s. Let's compare this annual data with the rest of the data, 0.69 m³/s year in 2020, 1.094 m³/s year in 2021, 1.141 m³/s year in 2022, and 1.12 m³/s year in 2023 is doing. From this, it can be concluded that since 2019, the flow of the Jinnidarya river has been decreasing.

6-graph. Graph of annual changes in Aksuvdarya river flow (Aksuvdarya-Khisarak hydropost).

7-graph. The graph of the annual change of the Kashkadarya river flow at hydroposts.

The data from the hydro-posts along the Qashqadaryo River basin has been analyzed over the years. These data reveal the annual variations in flow, similar to the example of the Yakkabog'daryo. Annual flow quantities for the following years have been provided. These data allow for a brief analysis based on the average annual change in flow. To determine indicators of annual flow variations, we calculate the following indicators.

Based on the annual flow variations of the Qashqadaryo River and its main tributaries, we can summarize the following conclusions:

1. Qashqadaryo River in Varganza provides hydrological data that can be summarized as follows: between 1980 and 2020, the river discharge varied significantly depending on hydro-meteorological conditions. For example, years like 1986 (Annual average = 1.43 m³/s), 2000 (Annual average = 2.89 m³/s), and 2001 (Annual average = 2.15 m³/s) were noted as low discharge years. Conversely, 1992 (Annual average = 7.62 m³/s) and 1993 (Annual average = 9.68 m³/s) were years with high water flow observed in the river monitoring period.
2. According to the data of the Tanhozdaryo river Qatagon hydropost, in 1984 (Qort. year = 1.78 m³/s), in 1986 (Qort. year = 1.54 m³/s) and in 2001 (Kort.yil = 1.60 m³/s) during the studied period, there were low water years, while in 1992 (Kort.yil = 6.42 m³/s), we can see that 1998 (Quart. year = 8.76 m³/s) and 2012 (Quart. year = 6.65 m³/s) were recorded years of high water.

3. If we analyze the average annual water consumption data observed at the Aksuvdarya Khazarnova hydropost, in 1986 (Quart. year = 6.22 m³/s), in 2011 (Quart. year = 6.90 m³/s) and 2018 (Kort. year = 6.73 m³/s) were observed in the river, while in 1993 (Kort. year = 17.9 m³/s) and in 2005 (Kort. year .year =19.3 m³/s) years of high water were observed in the river.
4. If we look at the data observed at the Yakkabog Darya Tatar hydropost, in 1986 (Kort. year = 3.11 m³/s) and in 2001 (Kort. year = 2.08 m³/s) in the river During the studied period, the least watery years were observed in 1992 (Kort. year = 8.19 m³/s), in 1998 (Kort. year = 8.78 m³/s), in 2005 (Quart. year = 8.96 m³/s) and 2019 (Quart. year = 9.27 m³/s) were recorded years of high water in the river.

2-table. Information on consumption and mineralization of drainage water of main and inter-household collectors in Kashkadarya region

№ № p/ p	ye ars	Meas ure unit	months												Ann ual avar age
			I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VII I	IX	X	XI	XII	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
1	20 20	m ³ /s	37,5 6	36,6 4	36,3 1	31,1 3	28,0 0	26,4 8	23,6 2	18, 42	18, 94	23, 15	34, 66	34,9 2	29,1 5
		mln/ m ³	100, 59	88,6 4	97,2 5	80,6 9	74,9 7	68,6 4	63,9 4	49, 32	49, 08	61, 99	89, 83	93,5 1	918, 45
		g/l	4,91	4,92	5,11	6,02	5,29	5,04	3,50	5,2 5	5,4 2	5,2 8	5,1 3	5,98	5,12
2	20 21	m ³ /s	37,4 56	34,9 09	47,3 82	52,6 2	153, 48	46,5 6	41,1 9	30, 18	27, 47	30, 22	35, 56	38,5 7	39,7 2
		mln/ m ³	100, 306	84,4 46	126, 889	136, 40	143, 23	120, 68	110, 29	80, 83	71, 21	80, 94	94, 77	103, 29	1253 ,28
		g/l	5,54	5,10 8	5,04 8	5,14	5,08	4,68	4,18	4,6 6	4,5 9	4,6 2	4,6 0	4,41	4,83
3	20 22	m ³ /s	40,8 4	39,0 7	41,1 5	57,6 6	61,9 3	41,0 5	39,7 7	34, 57	29, 97	31, 07	33, 40	41,2 5	40,9 8
		mln/ m ³	109, 38	97,9 0	110, 22	149, 44	165, 87	106, 41	106, 52	92, 59	77, 68	83, 22	86, 58	110, 49	1296 ,32
		g/l	4,39	4,09	4,97	4,66	4,46	4,95	4,94	4,7 5	5,3 6	4,3 5	4,6 6	4,46	4,65
4	20 23	m ³ /s	47,6 6	38,9 8	42,5 4	37,2 2	24,2 3	19,1 4	16,4 8	18, 79	14, 37	17, 00	23, 33	23,4 8	26,9 6
		mln/ m ³	127, 64	94,3 1	113, 94	96,4 7	64,9 0	49,6 1	44,1 5	50, 33	37, 25	45, 53	60, 46	62,8 9	847, 49
		g/l	4,62	4,53	4,50	5,16	6,53	4,83	4,90	4,9 6	5,3 9	4,9 4	4,9 6	4,55	4,85

3—table. Comparative assessment of water-salt balance of irrigated areas of Kashkadarya region in 2016-2023.

№ № p/p	Years	Water ingress		The amount of salts, thousand tons	Water discharge		Salts output thousand tons	Salt balance thousand tons
		Taken for irrigation total amount of water	of irrigation water mineralization g/l		Flow to KDT consumption of water	Salinity g/l		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
<u>2016-2019 yillar uchun</u>								
1	2016	4201,05	1,11	4645,61	1425,99	4,87	6945,61	-2300,0
2	2017	4506,11	1,18	5325,89	1313,13	4,92	6460,14	-1134,25
3	2018	4353,73	1,057	4822,12	1366,19	4,673	6384,09	-1561,97
4	2019	4903,56	1,085	5321,07	1757,04	4,86	8539,52	-3218,45
	o'rtacha	4491,11	1,108	5028,67	1465,59	4,83	7082,34	-2053,67
<u>2020-2023 yillar uchun</u>								
1	2020	3801,74	1,04	3935,62	918,45	5,17	4751,22	-815,59
2	2021	5100,91	1,05	5369,32	1253,28	4,83	6052,80	-683,48
3	2022	4733,79	1,01	4766,71	1296,36	4,65	6034,13	-1267,41
4	2023	3834,86	1,05	4030,44	847,49	4,85	4110,32	-79,88
	o'rtacha	4367,83	1,04	4525,52	1078,90	4,88	5237,12	-711,60

1.4.2-Image. Salt content of irrigation water at the inlet and outlet of the irrigated fields of Qamashi district (g/l).

The water intake and drainage ratio is 22.1 percent. Water drainage per hectare is 1648.91 cubic meters/hectare. The average annual mineralization of wastewater is 4.85 g/l. Drainage module -0.08 l/sec. 5237.12 thousand tons of salt came out through the collector drains.

In the Kashkadarya region, outside the Kitab-Shakhrisabz irrigation area, one of the main features that defines the direction of hydrogeological processes and the regime of underground waters is the particularly challenging nature of groundwater flow. Expanding agricultural fields primarily in irrigated areas, developing large irrigation facilities, improving rural water supply with water, and taking other measures contribute to the sensitive change of natural conditions, particularly redistributing underground water flow, organizing them, and influencing hydrogeological conditions. However, in 2020-2023, the amount of water allocated for irrigation decreased by 348.48 million cubic meters compared to 2016-2019, and the amount of irrigation water drained from the collector-drainage system also decreased by 386.89 m³. This, in turn, led to a decrease in the amount of salt discharged by 1,845.22 thousand tons. Eventually, it led to an increase in the amount of salt found in the areas under study.

Before discussing the process of deposition and the modern state of accumulation in terms of chemical composition, let's consolidate the information regarding the denudation area.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be noted that the amount of dry residue and basic ions in groundwater in all sub-regions has decreased. Groundwater desalination involves, on the one hand, the use of fresh surface water to irrigate crops, and on the other hand, the introduction of easily soluble salts during saturation of the moisture-saturated part of the aeration zone from below. Based on the annual fluctuation graphs of the flow of the Kashkadarya and its major tributaries, 2019 was a year of high water in the river, and the water flow in these rivers will decrease in the following years. The total irrigated area of Kitab district is 20,276 thousand hectares, the experimental field plot is 3.6 hectares. A water-saving irrigation system was installed on the demonstration site. Mineralization of irrigation water is 0.25-0.4 mg/l. Water-saving irrigation systems, soil moisture VWC %, temperature 0C, electrical conductivity YeC, mS/cm, as well as equipment for continuous monitoring of the level, temperature and mineralization of underground water were installed in the demonstration plots in Qamashi and Karshi districts. Groundwater is also used for irrigation in a field experimental plot in Karshi district. Calibration of the equipment installed at the demonstration sites in Qamashi and Karshi districts was carried out jointly under the leadership of a Japanese professor. The reclamation condition of more than half (57%) of the irrigated fields in the Kashkadarya river basin, especially in Karshi and Qamashi districts, and all (100%) of the irrigated fields in Kitab district was assessed as good. The reclamation condition of the irrigated fields in the experimental field plots in Kitab, Qamashi and Karshi districts was assessed as good. The soil is not saline.

The analysis results revealed that in the Qarshi district, 49% (24,630 ha) of irrigated fields have groundwater mineralization levels ranging from 1 to 3 g/l, 40% have levels from 3 to 5 g/l, and 11% have levels from 5 to 10 g/l. In Qamashi district, 30% of irrigated fields have groundwater mineralization levels of 0-1 g/l, 27% have levels of 1-3 g/l, 16% have levels of 3-5 g/l, 25% have levels of 5-10 g/l, and the remaining 2% have levels exceeding 10 g/l. In Kitob district, nearly all (100%) of the irrigated fields have groundwater mineralization levels below 1 g/l. This indicates that Kitob district, being situated in a zone where groundwater occurs naturally, maintains consistently low mineralization levels, while in Kamarshi and Qarshi districts located in middle and lower reaches, respectively, varying levels of groundwater mineralization are observed.

REFERENCES

1. Wang, X., Chen, Y., Li, Z., Fang, G., & Wang, Y. (2020). Development and utilization of water resources and assessment of water security in Central Asia. *Agricultural Water Management*, 240, 106297.
2. Salokhiddiov, A., Khakimova, P., Ismailov, M., Razzakov, R., & Mirzaqobulov, J. (2020, July). Impact of Climate Change on Irrigated Agriculture in steppe Zones of Uzbekistan. In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* (Vol. 883, No. 1, p. 012073). IOP Publishing.
3. Kulmatov, R., Groll, M., Rasulov, A., Soliev, I., & Romic, M. (2018). Status quo and present challenges of the sustainable use and management of water and land resources in Central Asian irrigation zones-The example of the Navoi region (Uzbekistan). *Quaternary international*, 464, 396-410.

4. Obidov, Z., Dodoboev, Y., & Homidov, B. (2019, May). Innovative development of agricultural production in Uzbekistan: condition and prospects. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 274, No. 1, p. 012104). IOP Publishing.
5. Yuldashev, N. K., Nabokov, V. I., Nekrasov, K. V., & Tursunov, B. O. (2020). Modernization and intensification of agriculture in the republic of Uzbekistan. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 222, p. 06033). EDP Sciences.
6. Turaeva, S., & Sultanova, G. (2023). Climate Change Impact on Agriculture and Water Resources: Uzbekistan. In *SDGs in the Asia and Pacific Region* (pp. 1-21). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
7. Kattakulov, F., Artikbekova, F., Gafurov, Z., Jumabaeva, G., & Musulmanov, F. (2021). Consideration of climatic factors in the operating mode of hydraulic facilities in the Amudarya river basin. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 264, p. 03068). EDP Sciences.
8. Olsson, O., Gassmann, M., Manig, N., Ikramova, M., & Wegerich, K. (2013). Basin efficiency approach and its effect on streamflow quality, Zerafshan River Uzbekistan. *Journal of Hydrology*, 476, 128-135.
9. Suyunov, A., Aminjanova, M., Khushmurodov, F., Usmanova, R., Erdonov, L., Mukumova, H., ... & Sultanov, S. (2024). The impact of the hydrological condition of Kashkadarya oasis on the formation of agrolandscapes. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 539, p. 01016). EDP Sciences.
10. Yangiev, A., Adjimuradov, D., Panjiev, S., & Karshiev, R. (2021). Results and analysis of field research in flood reservoirs in Kashkadarya region. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 264, p. 03033). EDP Sciences.
11. Suyunov, A., Aminjanova, M., Khushmurodov, F., Usmanova, R., Erdonov, L., Mukumova, H., ... & Sultanov, S. (2024). The impact of the hydrological condition of Kashkadarya oasis on the formation of agrolandscapes. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 539, p. 01016). EDP Sciences.
12. Muzafarov, S. M., Tursunov, O., Kodirov, D., Togaev, B. K., Balitskiy, V. E., Babayev, A. G., ... & Allenova, I. V. (2020, December). Features of streamer form of corona discharge in respect to electric gas purification. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 614, No. 1, p. 012050). IOP Publishing.
13. Abdullaev, B. D., Razzakov, R. I., Okhunov, F. A., & Nasibov, B. R. (2023). Modeling of hydrogeological processes in irrigation areas based on modern programs. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 401, p. 02006). EDP Sciences.
14. Djumanov, J. X., Zaynidinov, H. N., Egamberdiev, X. S., & Eshmuradov, D. E. Mathematical Modeling of the Processes Formations of Stocks in Low Water Period (on the example of the Kitab-Shahrisabz aquifer). *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (IJITEE)* ISSN, 2278-3075.
15. Dadajonovich, A. B., Temirkhojaevich, S. A., & Ishkulovich, R. R. (2024). MONITORING OF GROUNDWATER QUALITY CHANGES IN IRRIGATED LANDS OF KASHKADARYA REGION. *British Journal of Global Ecology and Sustainable Development*, 27, 11-21.
16. Khamidov, S., Li, Z., Nasirova, M., Pulatov, B., & Pulatov, A. (2023). Assessment of temperature and precipitation trends in Kashkadarya, Uzbekistan. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 365, p. 01005). EDP Sciences.

17. Egamberdiev, N. B., Sharipjonova, Z., Nasibov, B., Khomidov, A. O., Alimova, M. I., & Abdumalikov, A. A. (2021). Biological treatment of industrial and domestic wastewater of a brewery in Uzbekistan. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 264, p. 01055). EDP Sciences.
18. Glovatsky, O., Krutov, A., Ergashev, R., Gazaryan, A., Rashidov, J., & Kholbutayev, B. (2023, March). Improvement of water intake in large machine water uplifting systems (on the example of the Karshi main canal). In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2612, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
19. Karimov, A., Bazatov, D., Kazbekov, J., & Rakhmatullaev, S. (2005). Groundwater use in irrigated agriculture in Amudarya River Basin in socio-economic dimensions. *Water District Management and Governance*, 581.
20. Khodjiev, A. (2023). Impact Assessment of climate change on water resources of the Amu Darya River basin. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 376, p. 02010). EDP Sciences.
21. Karimov, B. K., Shoergashova, S. S., Li, F., Talskikh, V. N., & Latisheva, L. N. (2022). Impact of agricultural development on water quality in Zarafshan River, Uzbekistan, Central Asia: Trends since 1960s. In *Current Directions in Water Scarcity Research* (Vol. 5, pp. 411-436). Elsevier.
22. Wang, X., Chen, Y., Li, Z., Fang, G., & Wang, Y. (2020). Development and utilization of water resources and assessment of water security in Central Asia. *Agricultural Water Management*, 240, 106297.